

The "Shaking Effect" on the Conductivities of Liquids*

G. RIESCH, V. GUIMANN* and H. SCHAUFER

Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, The Technical University of Vienna, Austria

Reports on the necessity to shake the solution prior to conductivity measurements are briefly reviewed. Conductivity measurements on dilute sodium chloride solutions revealed an increase in conductivity by rocking the solution prior to measurement. It is proposed that part of the energy provided to the system by rocking is stored in different degrees in the various hierarchic levels of the solution. It is proposed that the increased structural and energetic differentiation produced in this way is maintained dynamically and responsible for memory effects in liquids.

MEMORY effects in the solid state are well-established^{1,2}, but their occurrence in the liquid state is hardly accepted. As the high relaxation rates are further increased by increasing the energy content of a liquid phase³, it is usually believed that random distribution is more readily "established" as the energy content of the system is increased. However, random distribution is not a fact, but rather the outcome of the interpretation of statistical results. According to the statistical treatment, the so-called "mean values" are attributed to the different parts of the system. The consequences of this procedure lead rather to idealizations than to an understanding of the actual differentiation of matter, energy and information within the system under consideration, which appeared unaccessible so far.

One of the idealizations, which appears to make it difficult to consider seriously memory effects in liquids, is that of reversibility. This seems to have prevented systematic investigations on the effects of mechanical actions on various properties in the liquid state. All kinetic investigations are carried out under the action of mechanical forces and the same applies to many thermodynamic measurements. Shaking effects on the conductivities of solutions have been repeatedly reported, although usually just mentioned in the experimental sections.

45 years ago Hartley and Donaldson⁴ mentioned an increase in conductivities of various aqueous electrolyte solutions with time, notably in very dilute solutions. They obtained consistent readings after stirring the solution by completely inverting the vessel many times. Similar observations were made by Swift⁵ and by Monk⁶, who noticed that the resistance readings in the more dilute solutions drifted steadily. They reported that these effects could be overcome by shaking the cell. Such effects were also observed by James⁷. The opposite effect, namely a decrease in conductivity after shaking was found for highly purified water⁸. Because shaking produced an increase in conductivity in the presence

of traces of ammonia, these effects were attributed to the removal and introduction of carbon dioxide respectively. Guimann,⁹⁻¹³ repeatedly mentioned the necessity of prolonged shaking or stirring various non-aqueous solutions prior to resistance measurements. Ames and Sears¹⁴ also reported the increase in conductivities in more dilute solutions, even though temperature equilibrium had been established. They found the measured resistance reproducible, if the cells were manually manipulated in a manner as to change the solution between the electrodes immediately prior to measurement.

Prue and Sherrington¹⁵ found that even after thermal equilibrium had been established, the resistance of the solutions decreased slightly with time; the resistances determined immediately after rocking the cell were constant within the accuracy of the measurements and were taken as correct. The so-called "shaking effect" was found more pronounced with aqueous solutions than with solutions in methanol or in dimethylformamide and much more pronounced the smaller the electrolyte concentration. The changes in resistance 20 min after rocking the cell were up to 30% for the pure solvents, but hardly measurable at concentrations well above 10^{-3} M.

More recently, similar memory effects have been reported for the electric conductivity in liquid metal alloys. Miller, Paces and Komarek¹⁶ found that the conductivities of liquid cadmium-antimony alloys containing 60 to 70% cadmium increase smoothly with increasing temperature, the liquid being mixed quite thoroughly before any readings were taken. They found the values at any given temperature different on initial heating and on subsequent cooling. After the initial heating-cooling cycle, the conductance data, on further cycling, reproduced the cooling curves. It may be mentioned in this connection that Scheil and Baach¹⁷ observed that the activity of cadmium in cadmium-antimony melts is dependent on the

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history of the melt, and that liquids formed by melting the stable solid have a lower activity than melts which had been heated well above the liquidus temperature.

Thus, shaking and memory effects appear well-established for various electrolyte solutions as well as for metallic melts. They depend not only on the nature of the solvent and of the solute but also on the concentration of the latter. It has been suggested by various authors that the shaking effect for electrolyte solutions may be due to changes in concentrations of dissolved gases but experiments under defined conditions appear not to have been made. It has also been suggested that the effects may also depend on the nature of the electrode and the highly specific interaction between electrode and solution^{4,7,10}.

Experimental

$10^{-1} M$ stock solutions of NaCl in distilled water were prepared and stepwise diluted to $c=10^{-2}$, 10^{-3} and 10^{-4} respectively. Conductivity measurements were carried out at $22.30 \pm 0.03^\circ$ by means of a Wayne Kerr Autobalance Universal Bridge B 642 and a thermostated cell with blank platinum electrodes (cell constant at 0.3583 cm^{-1}). The temperature in the cell was measured by a Lauda digital thermometer, which was removed from the solution as the reading was taken.

Measurements were made before and after rocking the sample by hand about 150 times in one minute. By this procedure the temperature of a 100 ml sample of the solution was found to increase by about 1.8° . Specific effects between electrode and solution in the course of rocking have been excluded by carrying out the rocking in Erlenmeyer flasks prior to introduction into the conductivity vessel. After full thermal equilibrium has been established, the conductivities were measured and

TABLE I—SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITIES OF NaCl SOLUTIONS IN $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$.

w: obtained by dilution *without* rocking
r: *rocked*.

$10^{-1} M$	$10^{-2} M$	$10^{-3} M$
3.12×10^{-3}	8.40×10^{-4}	1.142×10^{-4}
		1.555×10^{-4}
	8.70×10^{-4}	1.161×10^{-4}
		1.165×10^{-4}
3.38×10^{-3}	8.60×10^{-4}	1.165×10^{-4}
		1.180×10^{-4}
	8.70×10^{-4}	1.174×10^{-4}
		1.171×10^{-4}

found persistently higher after rocking the cell. For a $10^{-3} M$ solution the amount of dissolved oxygen was measured polarographically and found 2.18×10^{-3} mole O_2 /litre. The oxygen content was found to increase by the action of rocking to 2.33×10^{-3} mole O_2 /litre.

The results show that at different NaCl concentrations the solutions had higher conductivities after rocking. Such rocking effects were partly preserved even through the dilution steps. No decrease was observed on standing for 2 weeks.

Discussion

The results cannot be interpreted on ground of the current views. Structural, thermodynamic and kinetic data do not provide access to the differentiations within a given system. According to a non-statistical approach proposed recently¹⁸⁻²⁵ the structural differentiation which is disguised in the statistical data²⁶, has been illustrated by the application of the so-called bond length variation rules of the extended donor-acceptor approach^{23,27}. It has been shown that such differentiations must be dynamically maintained and highly influenced by the actual environmental conditions^{18,19,23}. The strictly determined individual motions require the existence of relations between stronger and weaker, outside and inside, before and after.

The properties of the parts constituting the phase under consideration are different with regard to their energy content per part, their adaptability towards changes, their influence on the environment and their capability to accept and to store energy and information²⁸. The ordering with regard to their individual significance within the whole phase and for the whole phase has lead to distinguish different groups of particles. The continuous inter-relationships between them are characteristic for a so-called "hierarchical order" as reflected in the "hierarchical organization" of the parts within the system¹⁸⁻²⁸. In each of the different groups the parts are found to serve the system in different ways, i. e., on different hierarchic levels. A level is hierarchically higher the greater its significance for the whole system, the greater its range of influence, its adaptability towards changes, the energy content and the energy storage capability per part¹⁹.

The highest observable hierarchic level within a condensed phase is that of the phase boundary, which is continuously changing according to its dynamic interactions with the environment and with the other parts of its phase^{18,20}. The parts serving this level are not in thermal equilibrium and hence they may contain information about the history of the system. The historical information is not completely lost, although the parts are continuously exchanged between the levels. This is because information is not stored within the single parts of the system themselves, but maintained by the ordered dynamics within the collective²⁸.

The dissolved particles as well as the so-called "voids" influence each other "through" the "solution-structure" and they are under the decisive influence of the forces acting on the surface level. They have been referred to as "structure modifying and modified centres" ("SMM-centres"). They exert a decisive influence on the system properties. Solute particles, such as ions serve on a level which is hierarchically superior to that of the so-called "uncoordinated" solvent molecules, which may be referred to as "normal solvent molecules".

By the application of mechanical forces to a solid material, such as grinding or the action of cold-work, part of the energy applied remains in the system, where it is distributed over the various hierarchic levels according to their different adaptabilities²⁹. Thus, the system is increased in structural and in energetic differentiation in that it mobilizes its own dynamic order to maintain its "individuality"²⁹.

Likewise, shaking or stirring a solution leads to a limited energy increase of the system. The total gain in energy may be statistically insignificant and too small to be measurable, and yet it may result in a more or less pronounced increase in structural and energetic differentiation within the liquid system. The parts in higher levels gain energy, whereas the parts in the lowest level may even be lowered in energy. The number and stabilities of voids appear to be increased. This is in agreement with the increase in oxygen content found after rocking, although it cannot be said in what way the dissolved oxygen contributes to the system stabilization.

The slightly exothermic dissolution process of sodium chloride in water leads to a lowering of the total energy content of the system. The dissolved ions gain energy and become more strongly hydrated. Thus, energy must be provided from the vast amount of the so-called "normal" solvent molecules. Due to their large number, the energy loss per solvent molecule is unmeasurably small but the gain in energy per ion is more significant²⁹. The differentiation of the energy pattern is further increased by rocking the solution. Most of the extra energy is taken up by the ions. Each of them is stabilized by stronger hydration and also made more mobile; *the conductivity of the solution is increased.

The remarkable memory effect to the rocking treatment seems to be due to the gain in stabilities of the hydration structures, which are preserved dynamically in their leading role for the system properties. We have observed analogous memory effects after heating the sodium chloride solutions; their conductivities at room temperature are found higher than those of the solutions which had not been heated.

Likewise, the observations on the conductivities of cadmium-antimony alloys¹⁶ may be reinterpreted. As the system is heated, it becomes energetically more differentiated. In a metallic conductor the conductivity is decreased accordingly. The greater differentiation is not completely lost by lowering the temperature: after heating, the conductivity is somewhat lower and the ductility greater.

Vigorous stirring of a metal melt near its melting point leads to unexpected properties which are the basis of a new casting process, the so-called "Theocasting"³⁰. It will be shown in a forthcoming paper that such features are also explainable in terms of the concept of the hierarchic organization of matter.

Concluding Remarks

The unusual interpretation of the hardly appreciated "shaking effect" leads to a number of questions which may lead to appropriate experiments. It would be expected, for example, that by vigorous shaking of a highly diluted aqueous solution, its surface tension, its vapour pressure and its rate of solvolysis should change. It may further be expected that many other effects, which have been neglected so far, may find their place within the framework of the concept of the hierarchic organization of matter. In particular the question of interactions occurring at phase boundaries appears in a new light, as the hierarchically highest levels of both of the contacting phases are involved.

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* A reconsideration will be given in a forthcoming paper.

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